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RUSSIAN ANTHROPNOMY DEVELOPMENT IN THE MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE: ON THE EXAMPLE OF PERSONAL NAMES

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ANNOTATION

Russian anthroponymy development in the modern Russian language is considered in the article. Also, the main and distinctive features of proper names. The paper provides examples of personal names. It also talks about the specifics of studying names in linguistics. the article states that an anthroponym is a personal name, a characteristic of the individualization of an object: that each object (person) of a nomination has a name. It is further stated that the Register of names is limited, that personal names are duplicated, which is forced to give an additional name. The article claims that in a developed society, the official name of a person has the formula of his name.

Key words: anthroponym, Russian anthroponymy, culture, old Russian names, onomastics, Christian names, calendar names, baptisms, pagan names.

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РАЗВИТИЕ РУССКОЙ АНТРОПОНИМИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ: НА ПРИМЕРЕ ЛИЧНЫХ ИМЕН

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается вопрос развития русской антропонимики в современном русском языке. Так же основные и отличительные признаки имен собственных. В работе приводятся примеры личных имен. Говорится также о специфике изучения имен в лингвистике. В статье так же говорится, что антропоним-это личное имя, имеющее свойство индивидуализации объекта: у каждого объекта номинации (лица) есть имя. Далее говорится, что регистр имен ограничен, личные имена повторяются, что вынуждает давать дополнительные имена. В статье подчеркивается, что официальное имя человека в развитом обществе имеет формулу его имени.

Ключевые слова: антропоним, русская антропонимика, культура, древнерусские имена, ономастика, христианские имена, календарные имена, крещения, языческие имена.

Koziyeva Iqbol KomiljonovnaBuxoro davlat universiteti
rus tilshunosligi kafedrası o'qituvchisi
ikbolkoziyeva0105@gmail.com**ZAMONAVIY RUS TILIDA RUS ANTROPONIMIYASINING RIVOJLANISHI: SHAXSIY ISMLAR MISOLIDA****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy rus tilida rus antroponimikasini rivojlantirish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, tegishli ismlarning asosiy va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. Ishda shaxsiy ismlarning namunalari keltirilgan. Shuningdek, tilshunoslikda ismlarni o'rganishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari haqida gap boradi. Maqolada antroponim shaxsiy ism, ob'ektning individualizatsiyasining o'ziga xos xususiyatiga ega ekanligi: nominatsiyaning har bir ob'ekti (shaxs) ismga ega ekanligi haqida aytiladi. Yana nomlar registri cheklanganligi, shaxsiy ismlar takrorlanishi, bu esa qo'shimcha nom berishga majbur qilinishi haqida bayon etiladi. Maqolada rivojlangan jamiyatda shaxsning rasmiy nomi uning nomi formulasiga egaligi takidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: antroponim, rus antroponimikasi, madaniyati, qadimgi rus nomlari, onomastika, xristian ismlari, kalendar nomlari, suvga cho'mish, butparast ismlar.

The specificity of the study of names is that they are dominated by a linguistic component, and names develop according to the laws of language, however, linguistic at its core, it also includes ethnographic, historical, literary and geographical components that help the linguist identify the specifics of named objects and traditions associated with their naming.

Anthroponyms incorporate all historical, social, and cultural factors and reflect the usages of their time, the traditions of using personal names in different strata of society. That is why they are very sensitive to all the changes that are taking place. The composition of proper names in any language is not given once and for all. The repertoire of names is changing: some disappear from active use, others are created, and others change their place in onomastics. It is the change in the composition of names that is one of the most interesting problems of modern onomastics.

In recent years, research in the field of anthroponymy has been conducted in five main areas: the general theory of proper names; Russian anthroponyms history; the current state of Russian anthroponymy; anthroponyms in fiction; applied issues of anthroponymy.

The main distinguishing features of a proper name:

- it is given to an individual object, and not to a class of objects that have a trait characteristic of all individuals belonging to this class;
- an object referred to by its proper name is always clearly defined, delimited, and outlined;
- the name is not directly related to the concept and does not have a clear and unambiguous connotation at the language level.

Any object of reality can be called by both a common name and a proper name. It depends on a number of extralinguistic factors, among which the dominant role is played by the communicative need to designate the named object as an individual surrounded by communicating partners. The main differences between proper names and common names are that a common name not only names an object, but also designates, and only names a proper name; common names are ambiguous and can refer to several objects, and proper names are unambiguous and refer to one individual object, i.e. they relate only to one denotation and cannot to be a means of communication, unlike common names.

Thus, naming and identifying is the main lexical function of any name, including one's own. This the language function overrides all other functions of names highlighted in speech, and always accompanies them. The question of the meaning of proper names is controversial. Some linguists deny the meaning of the name (L.L.Guletskaya, A.A.Ufimtseva), others attribute greater importance to them than to common names (O.Espersen, E.Kurilovich), others speak of proper names that differ from common names (A.V.Superanskaya, V.D.Bondaletov).

For a proper name, the main thing is correlation with the subject and, speaking about the meaning of proper names, it must be emphasized that it is not equal to the concept of its appellative and is never limited to it. The meaning of a name is a factor of its fame, a socio-historical and extralinguistic factor.

At the language level, the semantics of a name is limited by the fact that it is a name; at the speech level, its semantics consists of an object-nominative connection and is accompanied by a complex of subjective information and emotional overtones, individual for each native speaker. In modern onomastics, there are several naming theories that try to explain the popularity of names. All these theories can be combined into three main ones: the social one, which claims that the name is a bundle of social information, and explains the choice of names by historical and social prerequisites (Isaac, October, Praskovya); emotional - the name is an emotional irritant, and the choice of names depends on how it sounds and what impression it makes; sound theory states that the sounds in a name have a meaning, of which the meaning of the whole name is formed, which affects its popularity.

The popularity of names depends on many factors that collectively influence their use. The problem of choosing a name and its influence on the fate of a person has been worrying people since ancient times. Plato in the dialogue "Kratilus" raises the problems of the correctness of the name and the relationship of the name and fate. P.A. Florensky does not doubt the strongest influence of the name on the fate of a person, Russian philosophers S.K. Bulgakov, N.A. Berdyaev, A.F. Losev give a description of proper names, which are the most important layer of language requiring comprehensive study.

One of the interesting problems is the name change, for example, aliases. Undoubtedly, when changing a name, they expect changes in life, and often it really happens, because the new name takes into account the life position of a person and his image. For example, the changes that occurred in the life of B.N. Bugaev with the adoption of the name Andrei Bely; changes in the life of V.I. Ulyanov, who became Lenin; in the world of show business, a bright and effective name is important, which can contribute to the popularity of a person, for example, Julian Vasin - Julian, Natalia Poryvai - Natasha Koroleva, Alla Ageeva - Masha Rasputina.

The name has some influence on a person, but it is more of a psychological influence. For example, from early childhood, a person with a strange name is faced with misunderstandings or obvious ridicule from peers (Autonome, Dazdraperma, Erast, Sandra), which lead to stress and, as a result, complexes that develop in a child from childhood, which leaves an imprint on the rest of his life. It is impossible to talk about the development of the Russian name system in the 20th century without having an idea of how it was built and developed historically. Russian name book formation stages are considered in the dissertation based on the materials of historical research of Russian anthroponymy. Russian names have two main periods in their development: pre-Christian and Christian; the Russian name system was subjected to four artificial interventions, which played an important role in its further formation and development.

Artificial intervention is called serious socio-stylistic innovations undertaken in connection with drastic revolutionary changes in the philosophical and ideological system of social values.

The first artificial intervention was the baptism of Russia, when they turned to Christian names that came from other countries and were associated with another culture. Before baptism, there were names Besson, Nelyub, Bryukhan, Wolf, etc., after the first intervention, names appeared Abraham, Criscent, Elizar, Agripina, etc.

The second intervention was the requirement to call only Christian names, and the Old Russian names turned out to be pagan. At this time, there is an increase in the number of calendar names, which is associated with the ban on Russian names and the search for compensation. This is an original way of developing the Russian onomasticon.

The third artificial intervention was in the XVII century, when, during the revision of church books, the forms of names well mastered by the Russian language were replaced by forms of the southwestern derivation, again receiving new names; Greek spelling, the letters "fita", "izhitsa", etc., began to be used, which made it difficult to perceive names. Therefore, the mass material mastered

by the people continued to live and develop according to the laws of language. For example, the colloquial names Aksinya and Aksinya are formed from the calendar name Ksenia, Oksana, Oksana; truncated Drone forms from Andronik, Gur from Gury, etc. At the time of Peter the Great's reforms, there was a sharp stratification of names: Western orientation was adopted in high society: Nicolas, Jean, Nelly, Natalie, names like Varvara and Vasilisa are common among the people, Arkhip, Ivan.

The fourth intervention is connected with the revolutionary events of the early twentieth century. Then a lot of names with ideological content were created, which filled the entire namebook of that time (Intern, Five-four, Aedile, Rocket, etc.). However, most of these neoplasms did not take root, because after the change of traditions that occurred with the adoption of Christianity, names with a prevailing common noun ceased to be typical for the Russian language. Thus, there was a return to the old fund of Russian names.

V.D.Bondaletov considers the names from the end of the XIX century to 1969 of the XX century (1893-1969), And Nikonov from 1970 to 1980, AZ.Suslova – names of the 90s of the XX century. According to V.D.Bondaletov, the top ten most popular names included: Olga, Natalia, Tatiana, Svetlana, Elena, Irina, Lyudmila, Galina, Marina, Larisa; Alexander, Nikolai, Mikhail, Vladimir, Sergey, Alexey, Dmitry, Andrey, Victor, Anatoly, Evgeny. The most popular names of V.A.Nikonov are: Natalia, Elena, Olga, Irina, Tatiana, Svetlana, Anna, Julia, Ekaterina, Maria, Oksana; Alexander, Alexey, Sergey, Andrey, Dmitry, Evgeny, Vladimir, Mikhail, Roman, Denis, Nikolai. Comparing popular names in the 60s, 70s and 80s, we note that at first the name Elena prevailed, and in the 80s it caught up with her Natalia; Alexander, Sergey, Alexey competed for men. Alexander is still popular with Suslova A.V., Sergey, Alexey, Tatiana, Natalia, Elena, and today the popularity of the names Nikita, Anton, Daniel (Danil), Denis, Pavel is rapidly growing, Anastasia, Ksenia, Oksana, Kristina, Ekaterina, Maria.

Thus, the central composition of the birthday people remains basically unchanged, its peripheral part is changing, which shows the state of the anthroponymic system. In V.D.Bondaletov's research, there were names that are popular now: Artemy, Maxim, Kirill, Victoria, Daria, Olesya. V.A.Nikonov began to meet these names more often, Polina, Kristina, Arina, Inna, Daniel (Danila) were added to them, Danil), Arseny, Nikita. In the name book of A.V. Suslova, the marked names are no longer rare, but are part of the names of widespread use and are popular. To observe the names at the present stage of development, statistical studies based on the quantitative and qualitative method of V.D.Bondaletov were conducted. This method of studying proper names makes it possible to compare chronological sections. A simple procedure for finding common names, followed by highlighting the top ten and top five most popular names among them, opens up the opportunity to focus on the most "crowded" part of the namebook. According to the processes taking place in this part of the namebook, you can get an idea of the qualitative transformation of the birthday boy, which, as the facts show, retains a fairly stable central composition and changes the peripheral part.

In recent years, Daniil, Ilya, Denis have become popular, Maxim, Artyom, Nikita; Arina, Daria, Alina, Varvara. The desire to diversify the birthday party leads to some negative consequences:

1) to the appearance of double names for naming children: Natalia - Natalia, Daria - Daria, Anastasia - Anastasia;

2) to use hypocoristic (in O.Sakhmanova's terminology, "affectionate") names as official ones: Sasha, Lena, Vika, Rita;

3) word-formation chains are used as official names: Danil - Daniel - Danila, Yana - Yanina; The influence of the mass media on the Russian name system is enormous. It is the media that are the conductors of those trends to which proper names are subject. In this work, the media is limited only by television, since access to newspapers, radio and the Internet is material for a separate study, here are examples The use of names on television is used only as illustrations.

An important factor influencing the popularity of names is fashion, one of the conductors of which is the media. The work highlights some of the fashion trends of today as a result of the influence of the media:

1) calling old names, at least as a pseudonym: Fekla Tolstaya (meaning the presenter of the Rossiya TV channel), Dunya (Avdotya) Smirnova, Polina Dashkova, Arina Sharapova, Daria Dontsova, Albina Grichina;

2) borrowing of foreign names, very often their abbreviated forms: Dan, Margot, Kat, etc.;

3) naming abbreviated forms of names: Gosha Kutsenko, Natasha Koroleva, Vlad Stashevsky, etc.;

4) the use of two-component naming instead of the traditional three-part Russian name book: presenter Vladimir Solovyov; Alla Pugacheva, or Alla Borisovna; correspondent Alexander Khabarov, etc. (the names of politicians are especially well traced);

5) naming children with the names of TV series characters: Alexander (became very popular after the TV series "Brigade"), Anastasia (after the TV series "Kamenskaya", etc.

6) imitation of public people: A. Malinin's children are named Frol and Ustinya, D. Malikova is Stanislava; Dmitry Nazarov's children are Arina and Arseny, which serves as an example to follow; A number of other factors also influence the choice of names and their popularity:

1) parents strive for the name to be beautiful, modern, in line with the spirit of the era, but this is subjective, individual and depends on a number of external circumstances, on the environment in which parents live, on the range of their interests, hobbies;

2) the factor of traditions, when children are named after grandmothers, grandfathers or other relatives;

3) The fashion factor plays a very big role. Fashion is dynamic, sensitive to the environment: all major events of world and national culture, phenomena of cultural life are reflected in the names. Children are often called by the names of popular writers, actors, favorite movie and book characters;

4) it can also be said that when choosing a name, there is also a euphony factor. Unfortunately, this concept is difficult to define. In fact, it is phonetic and associative. This is the general sound of the name, its appearance, which, however, is not equal to the concept of euphony in the theory of phonosemantics, where each sound has its own appearance, and from a combination of "good" and "bad" sounds, the euphony of the name is created;

5) the imitation factor is often detrimental. For example, wanting to give a sonorous name to a child, they take a foreign name without thinking about its meaning. Calling the girls taken from the posters by the names of Bayadera, Traviata, they do not think that they mean "harmful" and "fallen";

6) the choice of a name is also influenced by the factor of RAM (L.I. Raizenan and E.B. Magazanik). A person has a certain set of names in his memory, from which he chooses the name of the child, and this set is not very diverse;

7) the associative factor: various associations are associated with a person's name. For example, when naming a child, parents avoid giving a name that evokes negative associations in them;

8) a significant role is given to public taste, which explains the fact that some names are popular in one area, and others in another;

9) the father's name plays an important role in choosing a name, since the name and patronymic should be beautifully combined.

Personal proper names are distinguished by their originality and abundance of formative means, the ambiguity of forms of subjective assessment, and the richness of emotional shades in these forms. The originality is revealed in the production base, where there is a great sophistication, whimsicality of sound modifications and abbreviations. That is why the numerous forms of Russian anthroponyms are very difficult for foreign students to perceive.

The paper examines the ways of forming abbreviated forms of personal names and provides the most productive suffixes, with the help of which neutral (Tanya, Vanya), affectionate (Lenochka, Temochka) and pejorative (Masha, Svetka) forms of names are formed. Considering the concept of "the speaker's personal sphere" (according to Yu.D. Apresyan) in relation to personal names, it allows us to note that not all addresses with the suffix -ka (Tanka, Pebble, etc.) have a pejorative connotation, in some cases this is an appeal to a loved one.

For comparison, a parallel is drawn with the English abbreviated forms of the name and some recommendations are given for teachers. A distinctive feature of English personal names is their stability within the functional style (a person is assigned one form of Margaret is Peggy), in Russian you can use many variants (Kolya, Kolka, Kolka).

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